

Digressive Role of Women in Pakistani Media Domain and its Impact on society

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Discourse Analysis

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Abstract

Media is regarded as a platform of social transformation. The drama industry and television have dominated the media and is the most powerful domain. Pakistani society is complex where conventions, values, traditions and religion play a very important role in all the social classes however, this recipe for creating the content of Pakistani dramas is not followed by Pakistani media. This research aims to explore the digressive roles and portrayal of women in Pakistani media as the media industry creates content that allows women to exert their agency and power and break free from the cultural, social and religious limits. This research aims to identify discourse elements from Pakistani drams and to reveal how dominant features of media in representing women have normalized nontraditional women and the impact on women particularly and on society in Pakistani dramas “Mere pas tum ho” and “ Ghar titli ka par”. Interpretive qualitative research is used to identify discourse elements from these two Pakistani dramas.

Introduction

Discourse analysis is a research method for studying written or spoken language concerning its social context. It aims to understand how language is used in real-life situations.

The representation of women has long been central to feminist research. This is not least because mass media holds the power to mold and construct cultural ideals, to introduce young people and new audiences to social concepts they may not yet be familiar with, and to socialize young generations such that they do not readily challenge the established narratives of gender roles. The purpose of this research is to look critically at the way women are represented in the media on Pakistani Drama serials. We use some key terms of Discourse for analysis of the discourse of Pakistani Dramas.

Studies have established the fact that television serials depict primarily female characters as digressive, negative roles, liberal, dominant, rigid, aggressive characters in public roles and careers outside the home. My chief research question is, how are women represented in select Pakistani televised drama serials? There are two drama serials, *Ghar Titli ka par*, *Mere pas tum ho* both of them were extremely popular at the time of their release, as I witnessed their popularity myself and they were easily accessible to me on Netflix. Pakistani television plays have been ruling the entertainment industry on the whole given their intriguing plots and exceptional performances by the actors and actresses. The plays are usually family-centric and women always seem to play critical roles in them.

Though there remains a strong presence of regressive female characters, we can't deny the fact that our drama productions are evolving with time. Now more than ever, actresses can be seen portraying complicated, villainous roles with a dominant role in the story development. The credit goes to Pakistani script writers who have started adding a layer of depth when it comes to roles for women. The system lists down two actresses in both dramas who portray negative characters brilliantly. This kind of people cannot forgive and forget for a time. We saw Sanam Chauhdry as an antagonist Anji in *Ghar Titli Ke Paar* and Aaiza Khan in the drama *Mere pas tum ho*.

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The purpose of this research is to study the effects of Pakistani dramas on married and unmarried women's mental health and also its positive and negative effects on mood. The data was collected from two Pakistani dramas and different speeches and media. Results demonstrated that Pakistani dramas have a deep impact on the lives of Pakistani women but the effects are more pronounced on married women because most of them were housewives. Some of them like to watch TV dramas with their family but mostly they like to watch dramas separately. Pakistani dramas also affect the cultural values, language, religion and lifestyle of the generation. Mostly they affect the minds of the viewers negatively by showing the negative aspects of life. One of the big examples is Aurat March in which women played a liberal role. Media is playing a great role in making women digressive through dramas.

When Pakistan saw its annual Aurat March take place, the growing discourse around the March has given new negative impetus to Pakistani feminism. The women whose demands are now turned into charters of dramas are the same women whose issues have long been alien to the rest of the country. While the media tries to bring down these movements by distorting liberal slogans such as *Mera Jism Meri Marzi* (My Body My Choice), or *Khud Khana Garam Karlo* (Heat Up Your Food Yourself) — which is intended to highlight that women are expected freedom from the boundary of Islam too.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study is to explore how much T.V dramas are playing a negative role on women and what impacts are coming in society.

Research Question

What kind of negative impacts on women can be identified from Pakistani dramas?

The objective of the study

To identify discourse elements from the Pakistani TV dramas

Delimitations

Data is collected from only two Dramas “Ghar titli ka par” and “mere pas tum ho”

Methodology

Interpretive qualitative research

The methodology includes data collection, data analysis, results, and conclusion. It is important to use methods for research analysis that are appropriate according to the background of the study. TV dramas are the agenda of study.

Population

The total population is all Episodes of two dramas.

Sample

The total sample of the study is some episodes selected through the purposive sampling of two TV Dramas".

Literature Review

In the present age and period, the power of television and media cannot be denied. Sigman (2007). Baran (2004) has said that our lives are impregnated by the media. Despite the cyber revolution, television is an important and powerful medium to instruct, inform, educate and raise awareness. It strongly affects influences and shapes the thinking of the audience. Among the most-watched programs on television are the episodic television serials known as “dramas”. In an article published in Newline Magazine, Tasneem Ahmar (2012) is of the view that the portrayal of women in Pakistani dramas is far removed from reality. Mostly in the present drama women are depicted as extremely independent, liberal and progressive individuals who sometimes are seen to be breaking the standards set for them by their culture, society and religion. It has become common to portray women negatively as vampire-like and cunning. This depiction is invoking similar negative behavior, especially in the general public. (Tester, 1994, Thomson, 1998 & Litosseliti, 2006) observes that media tends to personalize, sensationalize and demonize their content to gain the attention of the viewers. Z Shakir (2020) analyzed the drama serial “Mery Paas Tum Ho” and his study suggests that Pakistani dramas should promote Pakistani and Islamic values, so television content can make a reason for the nation to feel proud. Iraj Mallick Iman (2021) researched the drama serial “Ghar Titli Ka Par” to discover the effects of extramarital affairs on the female audience and their perception that these depictions are normalizing extramarital affairs by men and the society.

The proposed research aims to analyze the discourse of “Mpasspaas tum ho” and “Ghar titli ka par” and study the non-traditional, negative and digressive roles of women that are deviating from the standards set by our society, religion and culture and its effect on society that has now started to absorb such discourse behaviors, particularly by women.

Tools

1. Code-switching
2. Privileged femininity
3. Resistance
4. Power
5. Self-discourse
6. Account
7. Cultural capital
8. Attitudes
9. Footing
10. Narrative
11. Access

Discourse representation

Drama no. 1: “Ghar Titli ka Par”

Parameter	Evidence	Remarks
1. Privileged femininity	Episode 8, 16, 18	<p>Anji says “meri Zindagi mein Mohabbat ka koi chapter nhi ” which shows her advantaged position in society because of her desire and achievements of being linked to powerful men of society. She knows how to manipulate her situation as she did in episode 8 with Kamran because Kamran is rich, handsome and an easy target.</p> <p>In episodes 16 and 18 Anji is seen to seduce Azir who is the husband of Shafaq.</p>

2. Access	Episode 10,19, 20, 21, 26	<p>Episode 10 shows access and manipulation of Shafaq's trust on her best friend when she says that Shafaq's family should ask Kamran before choosing such a dumb, boring and simple girl (Erum).</p> <p>Episode 19, 20 and 21 shows Anji's success towards her plans as Azir helped Anji and promised to help her in her needs and he started to get furious at Shafaq because of Anji's cunningness. When Azir says to Anji that they are good friends now Anji replies "Qismat daikhe na mera shohar mera hum mizaj hy aur na apki biwi apki mizaj ashna"</p> <p>Shafaq asked Azir in episode</p>
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		<p>26 that why is he getting too much worried about Anji and he said “wo tumhari dosti hai k nahi ye mujhe nhi pta magr wo meri dost jaruri hai”</p>
<p>3. Power</p>	<p>Episode 2, 3, 25, 29</p>	<p>Anji has power and control over her environment and people because of her dressing and her impression of being rich.</p> <p>The waiter in episode 2 got impressed by her status and beauty and instead of the slogan “udhar maang kar sharminda na hon” written in his shop, he offered Anji food and refused to take money. In episode 3 Anji says to her sister “ye ho nahi sakta k koi Anji ko ghaass na daaly” which shows her total control of her circumstances.</p> <p>In episode 25, Shafaq confirms Anji’s power and</p>

		<p>hold of Shafaq's husband by saying to her</p> <p>“Azir bohot badal gaye hain Anji, ab unke paas mere liye time hi nahi hota”. In episode 29 Anji has full fledged control and power over Azir and she asked him to divorce Shafaq so that Anji and Azir could marry each other.</p>
4. Connotation	Title of drama “Ghar titli ka par”	<p>Title connotes sensitivity of a home and the relationship of husband and wife is compared to the feather of a butterfly that is way too sensitive and can easily be broken. It also connotes Anji being the homewrecker of Shafaq and Azir.</p>

5. Narrative	Episodes 23, 24, 26, 30	<p>It can easily be witnessed in episode 23 that Anji is trying to pollute Shafaq’s image and character when she says that she had an affair with her cousin Hassaan. Episode 24 shows</p> <p>Anji was manipulative and captivating when she made up a story again when Azir asked her “tum office kis k saath aai ho” as she came to his office with an unknown person. She said that she has come with her very dear cousin Shakir bhai who was actually Anji’s neighbor and she was using him to pass her time. In episode 26 Anji fights with her husband who asks her to leave and she leaves her house. She tells Azir that Aftab misbehaved with her and also kicked her out of his house</p>
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		<p>without thinking of the sacrifices she made for him, whereas the actual situation was not parallel to her made up stories. In episode 30, Anji along with the help of a waiter, whom she has spent time with, tried to trap Shafaq and made a story which was not real. Azir got furious and said to Shafaq “ye Afzal wohi hy jis sy tm ny shadi ka waada kia tha”.</p> <p>Shafaq was a loyal and sincere wife but Azir was not ready to believe. Shafaq started crying and tried to prove her innocence to which Anji said “jhoot mat bolo Shafaq, tumhare maazi ki aik gawaah, mai b hun” Anji wanted to destroy Shafaq’s image, also</p>
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		wanted to take her status and loving husband.
6. Footing	Episode 8	In episode 8 Irum asked Shafaq to go out with her and Shafaq refused. Anji enters and Shafaq gets excited and happy and tells her that she was getting bored, as she start to dislike her sister in law because of Anji. Shafaq's change of interest is eminent as her alignment changes noticeably by the entrance of Anji.

7. Attitudes	Episode 8, 26, 33	<p>In episode 8, Kamran started making comparisons between Anji and his wife, Erum. In episode 26, because of all the manipulative games of Anji, Anji fights with her husband and Aftaab asks her to leave his house as he has fully developed a negative attitude towards his wife because of her activities. In episode 33. Azir discovers the true nature and personality of Anji from the waiter and understands all her lies when he says “mujhe yakeen ho gaya hai, na aaj na kal tum Shafaq ki dost kabhi nahi thi”. He develops a new understanding and new attitude towards Anji from now as everything has been revealed when he says to Anji “Shafaq dil o jaan se chahti thi tumhe aur andha aitbaar karti thi tum py”</p>
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8. Cultural Capital	Episode 2	Hassaan's mother said to him regarding his wish to marry Shafaq ``koi bhi khwab
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		<p>ankhon mein lagany sy pehly, apny halat zrur yaad rakhna”.</p> <p>Hassaan does not have a fancy house and cars and all the luxuries that Shafaq already has. Shafaq belongs to a well off family.</p>
9. Resistance	Episode 28, 30	<p>In episode 28 Anji said to Shafaq “Tum bahut bewafa ho aur apni bewakoofi ki waja sy aaj apna sub kuch khone ja rhi ho” to which Shafaq replied “ye mera ghar hy aur Azir mera shohar hy” which shows Shafaq’s attempt and wish to save her home and husband from Anji, she is resisting to the power of Anji.</p> <p>In episode 30, Azir furiously asked Shafaq to leave his house as Anji has successfully plotted against Shafaq by blaming that Shafaq had an affair with a waiter</p>

		<p>Afzal. Azir said “abhi aur isi waqt mere ghar sy nikal jao to which Shafaq replied “nhi Azir, ye mera ghar hy aur main yahan sy kahin nahi jaun gi”</p>
10. Account	Episode 33, 35	<p>Episode 33 shows an explanation of the waiter to Azir for his untoward behavior on seeing Anji who has told her name as “Shafaq” and also has taken gold jewelry and free food from that waiter as he said “mai iss k faraib ka dassa hua hun... is ny shadi ki dawa kar k mujhe dhoka diya hai”. In episode 35 Azir accepts all his mistakes and asks for forgiveness from</p>

		Shafaq. He explains his wrong
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		behaviors while accepting and apologizing at the same time “ mai janta hun main ne tmhary sath jo kia wo galat hy, mgy tanha na choro aur maaf krdo”
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Ghar titli ka par

The serial stars Sanam Chaudhry, Aiman Khan and Shahzad Shaikh in lead roles. The serial is about betrayal disguised in friendship. The story revolves around two college friends Shafaq (Aiman Khan), who belongs to a noble and rich family, and Anji (Sanam Chaudhary). Shafaq's family includes her father Atta, her mother Naheed and her brother Kamran. Kamran is engaged to his cousin Iram. Shafaq's family also has a close relationship with Naheed's sister (Shafaq and Kamran's aunt) and her son Hassan. Hassan likes Shafaq but is never able to tell anyone as his status is not parallel to Shafaq's (8).

Shafaq is kind-hearted and loved by everyone and quite rich, whereas, Anji is poor and greedy. Also, she takes pleasure by troubling others. She considers herself to be the prettiest woman on earth. She flirts with a waiter and constantly eats free food from his restaurant and takes a lot of money from him along with his jewelry (10). She flirts with a nearby grocery store owner and buys all the ration and luxury items for free. She constantly demands gifts and pizzas from a married neighbor. She befriends Shafaq just because of her money, because innocent Shafaq gifts her expensive things and also pays for her at the canteen always (2).

Anji soon understands that she can get easily rich if she marries Shafaq's brother, Kamran so she cleverly starts luring him and his family and flirting with him (1),(2),(3). Kamran is already engaged to his childhood fiancée, and cousin, Iram, who is very kind and loving and is very close to Shafaq also. But still, Kamran falls into Anji's trap but Shafaq's father gets to know of it and

quickly calls Iram to their house and tells her the whole situation and asks her to be alert and handle the situation. Anji is also very smart and she makes Shafaq start to hate Iram and trouble her and throw her out of the house (7). Soon, due to Iram's efforts and wisdom, Kamran soon understands Anji's true colours but still they're not able to make Shafaq know about Anji's truth. Iram and Kamran marry.

Anji repeatedly provokes Shafaq to take her revenge on Iram, and then marries an orphan boy of a well-to-do family in Lahore (1). Aftab tries to be a good husband to Anji but Anji is always rude to him. She doesn't look after her two children, Bunto and Munni. Her Bua (maid) is taking care of the entire house.

Shafaq also marries Azir and they shift to Lahore. The friends reunite in Lahore and seeing Azir richer and more handsome than her own husband, she gets so jealous of Shafaq that she tries to break her marriage. She tries hard to lure her husband and she is successful in doing so (2),(3). Azir kicks Shafaq out of his own house in front of Anji because of her manipulative games (5), (7). At the same time, Irum shows up and she takes Shafaq with her to Karachi.

After coming to Karachi Shafaq becomes pregnant with Azir's child. Irum tries to tell Azar the truth about Anji and also tells him about his upcoming baby. But he heard nothing and said he would only come to take his baby. Azar tells this to Anji, but Angie tells him that Shafaq is lying because if this were true then Shafaq would tell you herself.

One day when Anki and Azir go for dinner they happen to bump into the same waiter whom Anji used to flirt by telling her name as Shafaq. Waiter recognizes Anji and starts telling her cheating stories to Azir (10). Azir realises his wife is innocent and Anji is evil (7). He leaves Anji and Anji goes back to her mother's place. Azir pleads with Shafaq but she refuses to forgive him for cheating her and throwing her out of the house.

Drama no. 2: Mere Paas Tum Ho

Parameters	Evidence	Remarks
1. Power	Episode no. 1	<p>Danish works at an old-fashioned government office. Someone offers him a bribe and gradually persuades him, and he accepts it. The next day, though, he changes his mind. The anti-corruption raid at his office makes him nervous. He chooses to sell his bike to get the jewelry for her.</p> <p>Things change when he talks to his boss, who was bailed within two hours. To fulfill his wife's wishes, an honest guy is corrupted.</p>

2. Self-Discourse	Episode no. 7	Mahwish politely inquiries about his boss's wife, who claims he is upset by his wife. Furthermore, Mehwishwants to grow closer to his supervisor and expresses candor with him when she stops him from smoking.
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		Shahwar: “pata hai uska lahja kasa ha tum suno tohtumhain aag lag jai... ”
3. Code-switching	Episode no. 9	Mehwish said: “ap naraztoh nai han na...” Shahwar said: “ara nai why would i be upset mujhe pataha tumhari bhi family shohar ha ”
4. privileged femininity	Episode no. 10	Mehwish knock on Shahwar door and said “mai agala station per uterna chati hon Shahwar... ..” this show the how eager she is moved on from her poor husband towards a wealthyman
5. Resistance	Episode no. 12	Danish said “dekhna suna ma ap bara intelligent business man lagta han ap lakin yahan bhao karta howa ap na mujhe haran kardiya iss do takay ki larkika liya ap mujha 50

		millionda raha tha ” This
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		shows the Danish`sresistance to power
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Mere pass tum ho

Danish is a straight forward man with moral beliefs derived from romanticized Pakistani culture. He is a government employee. His entire existence revolves around his wife Mehwish and kid Roomi (the new child star). As a result of his flattery and the allure of his money, his wife Mehwish enters into an adulterous relationship with businessman Shehwar Ahmad. He even offers Mehwish a high-level post in his office with very high pay and additional advantages, but Mehwish's son and husband oppose her employment in his office because they suspect an extramarital relationship.

Mehwish eventually leaves her husband and children and begins a new life with Shehwar. She gets Shehwar to marry her after approximately six or seven months of living with him, but on the day of their wedding, Shehwar's first wife Maham returns to Pakistan. She is the only owner of Shehwar's fortune. When she finds Shehwar is planning to marry Mehwish, she smacks her across the face and orders her to leave her house immediately. As a result of Maham's imprisonment, Shehwar Ahmad loses both his fortune and his status, and he abandons Mehwish.

When Mehwish pays him a visit in jail, he refuses to recognise her and urges her to leave his life, blaming her for his wife's imprisonment. Mehwish has nowhere to go today, whereas Danish sold his previous flat and invested the proceeds in the stock market, becoming wealthy over the course of several months.

During these months, Danish forms a close connection with Roomi's instructor, Hania, but she develops romantic emotions for Danish. She even proposes to him since she loves him, but

Danish does not return her feelings. Mehwish, on the other side, seeks assistance from Danish's business colleague, Salman. He is also a common college acquaintance of theirs. She continually begs Danish's forgiveness via him and wishes to meet him once. Danish informs her, via Salman that he has forgiven her but does not wish to meet with her. She even attempts suicide, but Danish shows no care and fails to show up at the hospital to meet her. The media has widely reported on Shehwar Ahmed's prison sentence.

Danish agrees to see Mehwish once after being persuaded by Roomi and Salman. When he meets her, he has a massive heart attack as a result of having to face her and all the agony of betrayal that she has inflicted on him. He succumbs to his injuries at the hospital. Even Maham forgives Shehwar and returns him to the workplace, although he is demoted from CEO to a subordinate executive. This does not sit well with Shehwar, and he sees all of his errors and decides to leave Maham's house and life.

Analysis and Conclusion

There are so many negative impacts that have come on women through media. “OrateMarch” in Pakistan is also presenting the picture beyond religion. Role of media and mental health issues are some of the reasons for divorces that decreasing trust and tolerance in the joint family system.

Mera Jism Meri Marzi (Urdu: lit. 'My body, My choice') is a feminist slogan used by feminists in Pakistan to demand bodily autonomy and protest gender-based violence.

The slogan Mera Jism Meri Marzi has led to new slogans. Many placards in Aurat March found out work around with spin to main four words with similar notion such as Mera Jism Meri Marzi was discussed extensively on social media and many campaigns were started against it by rightists. It became a main tool in liberals' and rightists' war on social media with both defending their opinions and degrading others. It was also debated on national media with rights activists vouching for it and clergy calling it un-Islamic.

Amidst the Aurat March row, famous writer Khalil ur Rehman Qamar appeared on a talk show on Neo News where during debate he freaked out at the feminism activist Marvi Sirmed on interrupting him with chanting Mera Jism Meri Marzi slogan and made misogynist remarks about her and shamed her body which led to criticism and boycott of him by media fraternity. He was also criticized previously for some of his remarks which were thought to be regressive against women in the backdrop of his drama Meray Paas Tum Ho. All the discussion shows that media should show good portrayal of women that should not be beyond of our culture, social and religious boundaries. Critical discourse analysis aims to find out hidden issues and motives behind various discourses that are embedded in the society by examining them from a critical point of view. It scrutinizes how the more powerful groups of the society utilize political discourse to control and influence the less powerful groups for their advantage. The textual struggle for meaning is the precise equivalent of the social struggle for power (Fiske in Matheson, 2005). Because of the expansion of media, political talk shows have become both an intriguing program for the public and a large platform for the politicians to administer power and dominance over the society.

Through the analysis of two dramas of a television channel of Pakistan, the researchers attempted to reveal how the digressive role of women is represented in the society. It also suggests that these dialogues shows mystify the hidden meanings of language. In other words, critical discourse analysis reveals how these choices enable speakers to manipulate the realizations of discourse and power in the representation of action to produce particular meanings which are not always explicit for all readers.

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(Mansab, The Aurat March (Urdu: عورت مارچ or عورت احتجاج, English: "Women's March") is an annual socio-political demonstration in Pakistani cities such as Islamabad, Karachi, Lahore, Multan, Peshawar and Quetta to observe International Women's Day.[1][2], 2020)

(Kunthavi Kalachelvam, 2021)

(Habib, 2020)

(Meray Pass Tum Ho, 2019)

(Ghar Titli Ka Par, 2017)